

Towards a Psychology of fusion in the acculturation phenomenon

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Abstract

In the current paper, it was intended to approach, to report and to devise acculturation as an interactive and a dynamic phenomenon, in which the mutual learning is shaped by the acculturative motivations. Psychology is in a unique position to approach the phenomenon of acculturation, because learning and motivation are two of its main topics. The Brazilian culture, which is still in creation, and the Portuguese cultures are fitting in a research design that aims to check out, at the same time, the cultural maintenance, the changes, and the cultural mixtures. The Portuguese and the Brazilian cultures are still fitting in the earlier conceptualizations of the acculturation phenomenon written by Powell, by Simons, and by Redfield, Linton and Herskovits.

Keywords: acculturation, psychometrics, emic, Gilberto Freyre, fusion model.

Resumo

No presente artigo pretendeu-se abordar, reportar e operacionalizar a aculturação como um fenómeno interativo e dinâmico, no qual a aprendizagem recíproca é regulada pelas motivações aculturativas. A Psicologia encontra-se numa posição privilegiada para abordar o fenómeno da aculturação, uma vez que a aprendizagem e a motivação são duas temáticas fundamentais da mesma. As culturas brasileira, que se encontra em formação, e a portuguesa ajustam-se a um desenho da investigação que pretende verificar, em simultâneo, a manutenção cultural, as mudanças e as misturas culturais, sendo ainda que se ajustam às conceptualizações iniciais do fenómeno da aculturação concebidas por Powell, por Simons e por Redfield, Linton e Herskovits.

Palavras-chave: aculturação, psicometria, emic, Gilberto Freyre, modelo de fusão.

1. The definition of the acculturation construct

The acculturation phenomenon is defined by its main dimensions: the intercultural contact, the mutual interaction among the different cultures (Bourhis, et al., 1997; Redfield, Linton, and Herskovits, 1936), by learning a second culture (Powell, 1880; Rudmin, 2009),

and by the cultural changes at the individual (Graves, 1967), and at the collective levels (Malinowski, 1958). In the definition of the acculturation construct it is important to take into account that the cultural changes can do reinterpretation of the own cultural legacy (Barth, 1969), because the acculturation phenomenon is a dynamic process of cultural creation (Boas, 1982; Malinowski, 1958). It is still important to take into account that the acculturation process is shaped by strong motivations in all cultures.

2. The main models to approach the acculturation phenomenon

Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver (2006) stated that the acculturation topic has three models in order to approach it; the assimilation, the multicultural and the fusion model. Castro (2012, 2014a) added the intercultural model, which is supposed to be linked to the Francophone cultural legacy. The main features from the acculturation models will be described now. However, it is necessary to cast light into a theoretical detail. The words 'majority' and 'minority' are applied in the current paper, because they are employed in the pervasive Anglo-Saxon literature. It is necessary to standardize the concepts at the international stage, regardless that they should be targets of critical point of views. Hence, the accurate words would be the dominant cultural group and the dominated cultural group (Simons, 1901a, 1901b).

According to Castro (2014a, 2014b), in the assimilation model, the minority culture is expected to disappear, after to be completely adapted to the majority culture, and the mutual learning will not be reported on the expected outcome, because the minority will be assimilated into the majority culture. The European assimilation policies, during the 19th century, and the Chicago School conceptualization (Gordon, 1964; Park, 1928) are examples of the assimilation model.

In the multicultural model, the minority culture is expected to learn the culture of the majority, maintaining, however, at the same time, its own culture (Berry, 2001). In the multicultural model, just the minority is learning, and both cultures are only interacting in the larger society. It is important to notice that the larger society can not imply the segregation of the minority group, but rather a minimal intercultural interaction, which is backed by the

majority culture. The WASP culture (White, Anglo-Saxon and Protestant) is an example of the multicultural model.

In the fusion model, there are interactions and mutual learning processes between both cultures, and there are still cultural mixtures (Herskovits, 1938; Simons, 1901a), which will produce a new culture (Freyre, 1986; LaFromboise, Coleman, and Gerton, 1998). The emergent culture has internal diversity, because the different cultures are adding cultural features to each other (Bastide, 1971; Castro, 2012, 2014a, 2014b). The Brazilian culture, the Freyre (1986), and the Ortiz (1995) theories, or the policies of Alexander the Great (Simons, 1901a, 1901b) are examples of the fusion model (Rudmin, Wang, and Castro, 2015).

In the intercultural model, the minority at the private and at the individual levels can interact and can change. However, the minority can maintain its own cultural legacy, because it is applied the laissez-faire point of view at those domains. The minority at the public level is expected to get cultural adaptation regarding the majority culture, for instance, at the labor, and at the educational domains. However, the minority at the institutional level is not expected to interact with the majority culture. The universal values of the French Republic can be an example of the institutional level, because those values are not expected to change through the minority agency. In the light of this, the culture of the French Republic is an example of the model.

3. Culture and acculturation

The acculturation phenomenon is a way to generate culture(s), besides innovation and the cultural diffusion (Boas, 1982). Innovation occurs within the same culture, and acculturation occurs during the relationship between different cultures. Innovation, diffusion, and acculturation, as ways to generate culture(s), are often causing appraisals and concerns about the cultural changes. Moreover, acculturation is often an antagonistic phenomenon between the different cultures (Devereux, and Loeb, 1943; McGee, 1898), and the conflicts can even appear inside the same culture, because the reaction regarding the cultural changes can take different positions according to the different social classes (Castro, 2014a, 2014b; Navas, et al., 2005).

4. The lack of equivalence

In this paper, the theoretical rationales are supposed to be dependent and to be an expression of the cultures in which they are created (Bandura, 1999; Cronbach, and Meehl, 1955; Sinha, 1997). From a historical point of view, Psychology appeared in Europe concerned with the *Völkerpsychologie* of Wundt (Cronbach, 1957; Wundt, 1916). However, Psychology as a science was developed especially in the Anglo-Saxon North American culture, and its constructs, its dimensions, and its indicators are placed in that culture. From the point of view of the intercultural relationships, the Protestant culture of North America, namely the WASP culture, is characterized by the minimal intercultural interaction among the different cultures (Myrdal, 1944; Tocqueville, 2002; Todd, 1994). The Anglo-Saxons were employing a minimal intercultural interaction regarding the oppressed minorities, for example, the American Natives, the Afro-Americans, the Hispanics and the Asians. Yet, the discrimination behavior worked also towards the Europeans immigrants, because the Anglo-Saxons were discriminating the Catholics, the Orthodox, and the European Jews. However, more than the discrimination behavior, which characterizes the WASP culture, is above all the minimal interaction among the different cultures. The WASP culture is also not reporting the mutual learning. Thereby, it may be argued that the Anglo-Saxon culture, which is the pervasive in the study of the acculturation phenomenon, does not provide space for sharing cultural features in its theoretical rationales (Bowskill, Lyons, and Coyle, 2007; Castro, 2014a, 2014b; Rudmin, 2003), and consequently in the measurement instruments underlying them. The Berry Model (1974, 1997, 2001) is an example of what was stated.

Unlike the Anglo-Saxon culture, Castro (2014a, 2014b), following his doctoral thesis, revealed that in the Portuguese, in the Brazilian and in the Cape Verdean cultures are reported reciprocal learning processes. The Portuguese, the Brazilian and the Cape Verdean cultures are close to the fusion model (LaFromboise, Coleman, and Gerton, 1998), and those cultures are also close to the earlier conceptualizations of the acculturation phenomenon reported by Redfield, Linton and Herskovits (1936), and to the conceptual legacies of Powell (1880) and of Simons (1901a, 1901b, 1901c, 1901d, 1902). Moreover, in the current paper, it is still supposed that the fusion model and the theory of Gilberto Freyre (1986) are sharing roughly the same features.

According to Castro (2014a, 2014b), the universalistic ideas of the Catholic Church promoted the fusion of cultures, since the Catholics are perceiving the different cultures as

potentially 'equals'. The Protestant ideas (i.e. predestination) are favoring the individualistic position (Weber, 2001), and the minimal intercultural interaction with other cultures (Tocqueville, 2002; Todd, 1994). Therefore, according to Castro (2014a, 2014b), the Brazilian and the Portuguese historical backgrounds are different from the Anglo-Saxon cultural legacy. This cultural difference is raising the issue of the lack of equivalence (Poortinga, and Van Vijver, 1987) between the Anglo-Saxon and the Portuguese or the Brazilian cultures. The lack of equivalence is displaying that it is necessary to contextualize the researches, because the pervasive Berry Model (1974) does not fit in the Portuguese and in the Brazilian cultural realities.

In order to avoid the lack of equivalence in the acculturation topic, in comparison with the Anglo-Saxon culture, it is necessary to contextualize the research and to carry out a theoretical rationale on the Lusophone cultures, and in particular in the Brazilian and in the Portuguese cultures. The emic (Pike, 1954) conceptualization about the Brazilian and the Portuguese cultures can provide the groundwork to devise measurement instruments. Therefore, it is required to contextualize the constructs developed in the Anglo-Saxon culture to the Brazilian and to the Portuguese cultures. The acculturation topic has heuristic and analytical qualities in order to understand cultures and the intercultural behavior.

The Brazilian culture is privileged to accomplish this task. In the Brazilian culture, the acculturation phenomenon can be perceived at the same time as learning a second culture, as maintenance, and also as cultural change (Bastide, 1971; Sanchis, 1995, 2008). The creation of culture is a dynamic construction, because the different cultures are in intercultural contact, and because they are sharing cultural characteristics (Barth, 1969; Bartlett, 1923; Castro, 2012, 2014a, 2014b), allowing mixing cultures and the internal diversities. For that reason, this paper aims to approach acculturation as an interactive and a dynamic phenomenon, in which the mutual learning is shaped by the motivations (Malinowski, 1958; Rudmin, 2009).

4.1 Current situation and acculturation

As was stated above, acculturation may also be perceived as a way of learning a second culture during the entire lifespan, in addition to socialization and to enculturation. The socialization and the enculturation processes are occurring within the same culture (Castro, 2012, 2014a; Rudmin, 2009). Yet, acculturation is occurring during the intercultural

interaction between different cultures. One of the distinctive features of the human beings, in comparison with other animal species, is their higher ability to learn (Herskovits, 1967; Lévi-Strauss, 1986; Morin, 2003). Learning the cultural legacy is accomplished by enculturation and by socialization. However, today acculturation coexists simultaneously with the socialization and with the enculturation due to the faster human migrations, the increase of the available information (Serres, 2012), the easier and faster communications (Hobsbawm, 1995), and still because the ethnic identities are intertwined (Serres, 2012). Today, the ethnic identity is formulated beyond the tribe, the family, and the State in an individualistic and complex way (Bauman, 2004; Lyotard, 1988). Hence, the cultural influences among the different cultures have increased, and are affecting even the pedagogical practices (Compayré, 1889; Crossley, 2012). Moreover, today the national borders are more permeable, and the borders among cultures and among the different ways of learning (acculturation, enculturation, and socialization) are also more blurred. The growing number of the intercultural contacts can lead to conflicts, because of the interdependence and of the complexity in the intercultural relationships. Thus, it is necessary that each culture must be aware that the cultural legacies are done simultaneously between the changes, the maintenance, and the cultural mixtures.

To acknowledge the historical and the cultural backgrounds (Wundt, 1916), and an empathic dialogue (Rogers, 1975) with other cultures can reduce the ethnocentrism and can increase the tolerance and the knowledge about cultures, as Montaigne (n.d.) did when he wrote about the cannibals of the New World. To acknowledge the historical and the cultural backgrounds, and the empathic dialogue (Rogers, 1975) want to preserve the own cultural legacy, taking into account, however, its changeable characteristics. However, the preservation of the cultural heritage just seems to be possible under a negotiated position, and under a mitigated social dominance point of view (Sidanius, and Pratto, 1999).

4.2 Some implications from the current situation

In the material and in the technological conditions described above, the preservation of the cultural heritage works simultaneously with the cultural changes. Today, this phenomenon is enhanced thanks to those factors, representing a dysfunction of the assimilation model. For example, the Afro-American culture or its ethnic identity does not disappear, but rather is maintaining its culture. The contradictions are also present in the multicultural model, because cultures are changing permanently. For example, when a

minority is learning a majority culture, it leads to cultural changes, pointing out to the fusion model, and not to the cultural maintenance. Moreover, the majority culture is also learning and it is changing due to the minority cultural influence (Wieviorka, 2011).

The contradiction of the assimilation model is reporting the prevalence of the discrimination behavior in the intercultural relationships (Bauman, 1999; Teske, and Nelson, 1974). Yet, the multicultural model of Berry (1974, 1997) implies that the increase of the cultural contact leads to the disappearance of the minority cultural legacy. Therefore, the multicultural Berry Model (2001) is still placed on the assimilation model. According to Rudmin (2009), in the pervasive multicultural approach, the adaptation of the minority culture is perceived, at the same time, as the best option (less distressful), but also as a source of distress. This paradox is alike the Hispanic or the immigrant paradox, because the first generation of immigrants is reported to have a better health than the second generation, regardless the second generation is more adapted regarding the majority culture. Hence, the Berry Model (1974, 2001) can work well with newcomers (immigrants), but cannot work well with the minorities, who are living in the same territory with the majority culture for generations.

Nowadays, what remains from the assimilation model is the discrimination behavior addressed by the dominant culture (Bauman, 1999). However, discrimination, as Rudmin (2009) pointed out, is not acculturation by itself. The acculturation phenomenon is, above all, learning a second culture (Powell, 1880; Rudmin, 2009; Ward, 2010). Thus, the construct of acculturation returns to its original meaning, when Powell (1880) complained that the increasing contact between the Europeans and the Natives of North America, and also the increasing contact among the American Natives, were doing the research of the native languages too complex or useless. Thus, according to Powell (1880), acculturation (learning a second culture) was mixed with the enculturation of the native languages.

5. The goals of the current paper

Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver (2006) stated that the fusion model does not have any empirical study about its existence. However, in Brazil the culture of mixtures is a consensual reality, because of the Brazilians historical and sociological backgrounds (Bastos, 2012;

Braudel, 1943; Cardoso, 2003; Herskovits, 1967; Holanda, 1948, 2000; Meucci, 2005; Nabucco, 1908; Ribeiro, 1995; Velho, 2008; Verissimo, 1887).

In this paper, it was devised one general goal, which is leading to two secondary goals. The current paper aims to explore and to contextualize the Brazilian and the Portuguese cultures about the acculturation phenomenon. This general goal implies to carry out an emic theoretical rationale about the acculturation phenomenon, in comparison with the pervasive Anglo-Saxon culture (McGuire, 1973; Popper, 2002). The first main goal leads to a secondary goal. It aims to devise a measuring instrument adapted and contextualized to the Brazilian and to the Portuguese cultures, which will be grounded in the theoretical rationale.

The acculturation phenomenon implies cultural mixtures and cultural changes, besides the cultural maintenance. Thereby, acculturation is a dynamic process of cultural creation (Boas, 1982), and it is shaped by strong motivations in all cultures during the intercultural contact. The second secondary goal aims to broadcast the Brazilian and the Portuguese cultures, because they can be sources of soft power (Nye, 2011), taking into account the cultural challenges from the globalization process, and in particular in comparison with the pervasive Anglo-Saxon literature.

6. The psychometric operationalization

In this paper is presumed that will be possible to devise a Brazilian and a Portuguese theoretical rationale by approaching the phenomenon of acculturation as a dynamic process. The theoretical rationale provides the ground to devise measuring instruments adapted to the Brazilian and to the Portuguese cultures. Castro (2014a) divided the acculturation construct in eleven dimensions (Boudon, and Lazarsfeld, 1965): the interaction, the direction, the dimension of learning a second culture, the dimension of consensual, problematic or conflictive relationship, the dimension of the maintenance versus the cultural change, the dimension of the cultural mixtures, the acculturative appraisals about the cultural changes, the domains, the diversity, the dimension of dynamic versus static process, and finally the ethical appraisals.

In the work of Castro (2014a, 2014b) the four acculturation models (the assimilation, the multicultural, the fusion and the intercultural) are located in axes, taking into account the eleven dimensions of the acculturation construct. The positions of the models in the axes are representing the models as an expected outcome and also as a dynamic process. Besides, each dimension has an axis for the majority and for the minority cultures. The development of the axes allows a comparison between the observed outcomes and the expected outcomes. Thereby, the acculturation construct should be approached taking into account its dimensions, and its main models. Moreover, the axes are avoiding the exclusive application of proxies in the study of acculturation, such as discrimination, the socioeconomic status, the well-being, and above all the cultural preferences or the attitudes.

In the pervasive Anglo-Saxon literature, the cultural preferences or the attitudes are determining which acculturation model the individual is choosing. For example, if an Indigenous person from Brazil prefers the 'Brazilian' food and, at the same time, the 'Indigenous' food, he or she would be reporting a multicultural (integration) attitude. The Indigenous person prefers the 'Brazilian' culture, however without changing his or her indigenous cultural legacy. The integration attitude is leading to the Berry Model (1974, 2001), which is supposing that cultures are not sharing any cultural feature. In the Berry Model cultures, each culture is supposed to be uniform, and the different cultures are separated, even if the majority and the minority are living in the same territory for generations. For instance, it is the case of the indigenous tribes or of the Afro-Americans regarding the WASP culture. Thereby, the Berry Model does expect that cultures are sharing cultural features (Bowskill, Lyons, and Coyle, 2007; Rudmin, 2003, 2006). However, culture is dynamic, and the indigenous cultures of America are not the same as some centuries ago, and the Brazilian or the North American cultures are done by cultural contributions of several cultures, including the indigenous cultures. Hence, it is necessary to take into account that in the acculturation process the minority and the majority are both changing (Wieviorka, 2011), and both cultures are sharing cultural features.

The current paper aims that the acculturation construct must be formulated from the positions of the acculturation models, using the dimensions of the construct. The construct of acculturation should not be only devised employing the preferences or the cultural attitudes. It is also suggested that the same question must be answered by both cultures, and not only by the minority cultural group. The majority culture is also changing, and the appraisals about its cultural changes must be taken into account. Therefore, in the current paper, the questions and

their items will be devised taking into account the acculturation construct as a dynamic process.

The study of the acculturation phenomenon is shaped by culture and by History. Moreover, History has influenced the way that the acculturation phenomenon is approached. The need to return to the earlier conceptualizations of the acculturation phenomenon established by Powell (1880), by Simons (1901a) and by Redfield, Linton and Herskovits (1936), to question both cultural groups, and the need that the dimensions of the acculturation construct must be expressed in axes is connected with the ambiguity of the construct of acculturation itself. The ambiguity of the acculturation construct was reported in the work of Gilberto Freyre (1986).

6.1 The ambiguity of the acculturation construct

In the North American literature about the immigration phenomenon, the word acculturation is common. Yet Castro (2014a) in his doctoral thesis noticed that in the literature about the Portuguese emigration and about the immigration phenomena the word acculturation was rarely applied. However, the acculturation phenomenon is central in the Portuguese literature about the emigration and about the immigration phenomena. In the database of the *Observatório da Emigração* or in the Portuguese journal *Análise Social*, the word acculturation appeared rarely. On the contrary, on the website *Memória de África* ([Http://memoria-africa.ua.pt/](http://memoria-africa.ua.pt/)), which covers the Portuguese imperial history, the word acculturation appeared more than one hundred times in the bibliographic references (Castro, 2014a).

In the French culture, the word acculturation was abandoned due to its supposed low explanatory power, due to its ethnocentric meaning, and because acculturation supposedly led to discrimination, which entered into conflict with the egalitarian values of the French Republic (Brégent, Mokoukolo, and Pasquier, 2008; Sabatier, and Boutry, 2006). In Portugal, it occurred something similar to what happened in France, even because the last decades of both colonial empires were alike; with settlements and, after the mid-20th, with colonial wars, and there is also a historical sense of guilt and resentment. However, today the world is post-colonial, and many countries are living in an intermediate position on the

international scene. For example, Portugal (Santos, 1991) and Brazil have, at the same time, emigrants and immigrants and open societies.

The importance of the acculturation phenomenon emerges, because it contributes to the formation of culture by learning a second culture, and also because the human behavior is shaped by the cultural legacies, which are constantly remade. The world today appears increasingly interconnected, interdependent, and the subjectivity of the individual identities is increasing the cultural complexity.

Acculturation as an antagonistic process is reported by Freyre (1986), who considered the Brazilian society as being shaped by acculturation and, at the same time, by the intercultural conflicts. According to Freyre (1986), in Brazil, the main features from the Portuguese and the Brazilian cultures were the biological mixtures. However, the biological mixtures among the females from the oppressed cultural groups with the ruling European males were displaying an antagonist and an asymmetric meaning. The work of Freyre is displaying, at the same time, the race and the gender discriminations. Finally, it is necessary to state that the ambiguous meaning of acculturation is not avoiding that Psychology can approach it. But, on the contrary, the acculturation phenomenon is central to Psychology, because it covers the motivation and the learning phenomena.

7. Acculturation as a dynamic process and as an expected outcome in the future

7.1 The dimension of direction

Figure 1, the direction dimension as an expected outcome, majority position

The acculturation models are described in the following axes with the labels: the assimilation as As., the multicultural as Mt., the fusion as Fs., and finally the intercultural as It. In Figure 1, the acculturation models are represented as an expected outcome. In Figure 2, the models are represented as a dynamic process. The description of the intercultural model was suppressed in order to reduce the complexity. In the present paper, it is only displayed the

majority position, because the appraisals of the majority culture are often neglected. The study of acculturation is usually about and only addressed to the minorities.

In Figure 1, it is visible that in the assimilation model the direction takes only one sense of acculturative influences. The assimilation process provides a single, and an expected result in the future, and the cultural influences of the minority will not be reported in the majority culture. The assimilation model appears on the axis with a very negative value. In the multicultural model, the direction is based on the laissez-faire ideology. The direction is close to zero on the axis, and its value is negative, because the cultural influences from the minority will not be reported in the majority culture. In the fusion model, the process is reported as having two directions of cultural influences, being the only model in which this occurs, because the minority group learns a second culture. Besides, in the fusion model, the culture of the minority will be reported in the emerging new culture.

Figure 2, the direction dimension as a dynamic process, majority position

In Figure 2 is visible that just the assimilation model is not taking two-ways of cultural influences. The model appears on the axis with a negative value, though less than a result in the future because there is more interaction. The majority is also learning the minority culture. In the multicultural model, the direction of the majority is almost negative, because the minimal interaction implies only the cultural adaptation of the minority. However, as in the assimilation model, during the acculturation process, the ruling group can learn some cultural features from the minority culture. Although these features will be reported as belonging to the larger society. In the fusion model, the direction takes two-ways of cultural influences, appearing as positive in both axes, because the majority culture learns, and because what is learned is reported as such. Although in the fusion model the power relationship between the two cultures can be asymmetric. The two-ways of the fusion model are reported, for example, in the Brazilian literature of the 19th century (Cunha, 1984; Lacerda, 1911; Nabucco, 1908), and later on the beginning of the 20th century by Gilberto Freyre (1986). The main difference in the dimension of direction as a result and as a process is placed on the fact that all the

models are achieving more positive values as a dynamic process especially the multicultural model.

7.2 The dimension of learning a second culture

Figure 3, the learning dimension as an expected outcome, majority position

The learning dimension is displayed in Figure 3 as an outcome, and in Figure 4 as a dynamic process. In Figure 3 it is visible that in the assimilation model the majority culture does not learn any cultural feature from the minority culture. In the assimilation model, the learning process will not be reported in the future outcome. The model is appearing with a negative value on the axis. In the multicultural model it is expected that the minority would be learning the majority culture and, at the same time, it is expected that the minority would be maintaining its culture (Berry, 1974). Thus, the minority is reported as active in the learning process. However, the topic of learning is not addressed to the majority culture. The majority culture only allows the preference or the cultural attitude of the minority because of the laissez-faire; to learn the culture of the majority and simultaneously to maintain the minority cultural legacy. The value of learning in the majority appears near zero on the axis, but it is positive. In the fusion model, the learning process covers both cultural groups; the minority and the majority are reported as actives in the learning processes. Therefore, the majority is reported as more active than in the other models. In the Portuguese and in the Brazilian cultures to learn about foreign cultures is reported.

Figure 4, the learning dimension as a dynamic process, majority position

The learning dimension as a dynamic process is displayed in Figure 4. In the assimilation model, the majority culture is learning some cultural characteristics of the

minority, even because the interaction is maintained over many generations. The minority culture does not disappear as it was expected. In the majority, the cultural characteristics from the minority can experience reinterpretation in their functions, and in their meanings. However, as a result, the cultural characteristic of the minority will be reported as belonging to the majority culture. In the multicultural model can happen the same as in the assimilation model, since the majority group can learn some cultural characteristics of the minority. But, these cultural characteristics will be reported as belonging to the larger society. In Figure 4, the multicultural model comes with the lowest value in the learning dimension, because the model prescribes a reduced intercultural interaction. In the fusion model, the dominant group is intervening in the minority culture, sometimes in an antagonistic way, but it is also learning some cultural features from the minority. Moreover, the majority group reports the cultural characteristics of the minority in the emerging new culture. The culture of the majority still reports the interaction with the minority. Therefore, the minority culture is reported in the ruling one, which is leading to the cultural diversity and to a new culture.

The main difference in the learning dimension, as an outcome and as a dynamic process, is that learning is taking place in all the models, including in the assimilation model. Therefore, taking into account the positions of the models in the axes, the acculturation phenomenon should be approached as a dynamic process.

7.3 The dimension of maintenance versus the change

Figure 5, the maintenance as an expected outcome, majority position

Figure 6, the cultural change as an expected outcome, majority position

The dimension of the cultural maintenance implies its reverse, thus the cultural change. The dimension is represented on the axes 5 and 6 as an expected outcome, and it is

represented on the axes 7 and 8 as a dynamic process. In the assimilation model, the majority culture will prevail completely or the acculturation will be reported as such. There is no cultural change due to the influence of the minority culture, because the acculturation process is reported as an expected result; the assimilation of the minority. Therefore, as an expected outcome, the majority culture remains completely (see Figure 5). The model in the axis of the cultural maintenance appears with a positive result, and in the axis of the cultural change, it occurs the opposite, because the majority culture is not supposed to change (see Figure 6). In the multicultural model, the cultural maintenance is a fundamental dimension of the model (Berry, 1974, 1997). The multicultural model aims the cultural maintenance of all cultures in contact, although it is only reporting concerns with the cultural maintenance of the minority culture. In the majority, the model appears close to the zero in the axis (see Figure 6). The main contradiction of the multicultural model is reported because the majority and the minority are not expected to change, regardless both cultures are living in the same territory for generations. As Lévi-Strauss (1986) stated, the full communication with a different culture sooner or later triggers changes in the own culture.

The changes in the majority culture are omitted, because the dominant group is not expected to change with the minority cultural influences. In the multicultural model, the majority laissez-faire position can be just to maintain the majority culture unchanged. In the fusion model, the cultural maintenance is reduced in both cultures (see Figure 5), and there are changes in both cultures (including in the ruling majority). In the fusion model, the value of the cultural change is the highest.

Figure 7, the cultural maintenance as a dynamic process, majority position

In Figure 7, it is visible that in the assimilation model the cultural maintenance of the majority is higher than in the other models because the majority absorbs the minority. However, meanwhile the absorption of the minority culture does not end and the intercultural interaction remains, the majority can learn some cultural characteristics of the minority, changing its culture. Yet, those cultural domains are not reported in the expected result. In the multicultural model the majority culture is maintaining its culture, but at a lower value than in the assimilation model due to the Anglo-Saxon cultural characteristic of the minimal

intercultural interaction between the different cultures. In the fusion model, the majority culture is changing, and it is the only case among the models. However, if the power relationship between the two cultural groups is very asymmetric, the majority keeps some main characteristics, and it reports the mixtures separately, allowing, however, the cultural diversity.

Figure 8, the cultural change as a dynamic process, majority position

As it is visible in Figure 8, in the assimilation model the majority is changing because it is learning, and the majority is getting some cultural characteristics of the minority culture, which will not be reported in the expected outcome. But, as a process, there are cultural changes in the majority in the assimilation model. The multicultural model obtains the lowest level of changes because the minimal intercultural interaction postpones a larger interaction. However, the majority can change in some cultural domains, in which it is interacting with the minority. The position of the multicultural model on the axis is positive. The fusion model gets the highest value of acculturative change, which takes place in several cultural domains. However, if the intercultural relationship is very asymmetric, the emerging culture is separated in some domains, taking into account the internal diversity of the new culture.

In view of all the described axes, all cultures are changing, and the changes and the cultural maintenance are gaining more positive values as a dynamic process than as an expected outcome. Hence, the acculturation phenomenon should be addressed as a dynamic process, because the cultural changes can occur at the same time as the cultural maintenance.

7.4 The dimension of diversity

Figure 9, the diversity dimension as an expected outcome, majority position

Figure 10, the diversity dimension as a dynamic process, majority position

The axes 9 and 10 are representing the dimension of diversity. In the assimilation model, the majority can learn some cultural characteristics of the minority, because the assimilation process allows different results in several cultural domains (see Figure 10). The multicultural model gets the lowest value of diversity on the axis due to the characteristic of the minimal intercultural interaction, and also due to the cultural maintenance of the minority. In the Anglo-Saxon culture the internal diversity is not due to the intercultural interaction, but to the cultural separation between the different cultures. In the Anglo-Saxon culture, the cultural diversity is previous and it is independent of the intercultural interaction. The different cultures are living in the same space, but they are only interacting in a third cultural space; the larger society. In the fusion model, the majority is changing in several domains, even if the relationship is asymmetric, and it is getting the highest value of diversity on the axis. The majority is learning, and it is reporting the minority in the emerging culture.

Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver (2006) stated that the fusion model does not have any empirical study about its existence. However, the majority of the research designs are only approaching the minority and not the majority culture. The approach of the fusion model should also study the majority, the intercultural interaction, and the learning process (Castro, 2014a, 2014b). The approach of the fusion model also should take into account the antagonistic processes, because they can reveal the motivations of both cultural groups, even when assimilation is the minority preferred option. In further researches, it will be necessary to devise questions, which will be corresponding to the positions of the dimensions, and of the models in the axes.

8. Conclusions

The literature about the acculturation phenomenon is usually only reporting the appraisals from and about the minority culture, and it is not approaching the majority appraisals about its cultural changes (Geschke, et al., 2010; Rudmin, Villemo, and Olsen, 2007). However, Freyre (1986) reported that the Portuguese culture, regardless being the ruling culture in Brazil, was learning cultural features from the oppressed minorities. He also

reported that the Brazilian culture is diverse according to the cultural domains, because it resulted in a synthesis with several outcomes. For example, in the Brazilian culture, the Candomblé and the Umbanda religions are representing different cultural mixtures (Bastide, 1971, 1976), but both religions are the result of acculturation (Pierucci, 2000).

In the work of Freyre (1986), the mutual learning arises from the fact that the Portuguese majority was interacting in the same space and at several domains with the oppressed minorities. The construct of multiculturalism has several dimensions (Inglis, 1996), and the maintenance of cultural heritage is one of its fundamental dimensions. Another dimension from the construct of multiculturalism (Schalk-Soekar, and Van de Vijver, 2008) requires that the different cultures are living in the same space or territory, but the latter does not imply by itself the existence of an open intercultural interaction, and it does not imply that the WASP majority would be reporting the interaction and the learning process with the minorities.

The main advantage of Freyre's work (1986) is not only based on the fact that he is providing a positive value to mixtures, which was rare (Rodrigues 1934), in 1933, but also because he reported a majority learning with the oppressed cultures. Nowadays, the cultural of mixtures and the majority learning process are working as a consensual ideology in Portugal and Brazil (Almeida, 2004).

According to the author of this paper, the most important advantage of Freyre's work is grounded on the fact that his theoretical rationale is fitting in the current globalization process, which is interactive, in which cultures are interdependent, and the different cultures are learning with each other (Serres, 2012). The work of Freyre still works as a heuristic and as an analytical tool to understand the acculturation phenomenon because it was (and it is) a dynamic process of cultural creation.

Another advantage of the Freyre's work (1986) is to report that the acculturation process is often antagonistic. In Brazil, the acculturation process was carried out under strong motivations in all cultural groups. As Freyre accomplished, the acculturation process can be better understood, if the researchers have in mind the motivations of both cultures, and their gains and their losses (Rudmin, 2009) from their social practices, besides their cultural preferences.

The simultaneous use of qualitative and quantitative techniques seems to be the most suitable option for the study of acculturation. Regarding the quantitative techniques, the construction of axes through the fundamental dimensions of the construct and its models seems to be the best option. Besides, the current research aims to devise a research design that is close to the earlier conceptualizations of the construct of acculturation developed by Powell (1880), by Simons (1901a), and by Redfield, Linton and Herskovits (1936). The Brazilian and the Portuguese cultures are in a privileged position to carry out such task, because in these cultures it is possible to check out at the same time the cultural maintenance, the changes, and the cultural mixtures, besides, the interaction, the learning process, and the motivations.

Learning and motivation are two main topics of Psychology. The learning phenomenon is fundamental for humans. Lévi-Strauss (1986) stated that learning is the nature of humans, and to learn any culture is in our genes. Taking into account the motivation, as Lévi-Strauss (1986) said, it is hard to overcome a full and open communication regarding the strange culture, maintaining at the same time our culture untouched.

Given that acculturation is often an antagonistic phenomenon, it is necessary an empathic (Rogers, 1975) and a distant point of view (Lévi-Strauss, 1986) in order to approach the phenomenon, trying, in a precarious balance, to reconcile the changes and the tradition, the own and the culture of the Other. It is also necessary to extend that look beyond the human being towards nature (Morin, 2003), and still believing in the progress of knowledge (Elias, 1994), however taking into account the hazards of history (Morin, 2003).

Linton, in 1937, wrote about an American man who was concerned with the cultural changes in the North American culture. The American citizen did not notice that almost everything around him was done throughout the World History by many cultures:

“There can be no question about the average American's Americanism or his desire to preserve this precious heritage at all costs ... he will not fail to thank a Hebrew God in an Indo- European language that he is a one hundred percent (decimal system) invented by the Greeks ... “ (Linton, 1937, pp. 427-429)

Linton reminds us that the fears about the own cultural changes can be often an overreaction, and that culture(s) is done by a dynamic process, in which the maintenance is

working at the same time than the cultural changes, and in which cultures are mixing and are sharing cultural features.

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